

Phenomenal Velocity: A Step by Step Solution; Reasoning for the Method

Introduction :

The following solution to phenomenological velocity is algebraically deductive and essentially demonstrates how a mathematician can exploit an algebraic, "push-out," operation that makes 1 go to an existential v implicitly. This is the essence of the method used for solving phenomenological velocity as demonstrated in this paper. However, it should be noted that Mathematica continues to miss the fact that there is a 3rd solution to phenomenological velocity, which ought not be ignored (no pun intended), namely that v can be demonstrated as undefined with only the facts available within the original architecture of the initial formulation of the base equation. Our investigation demonstrates that *phenomenological velocity* is appropriately named, for the solution method demonstrated suspends the knowledge of the undefined expression for establishing a formal architecture of oneness, which is essentially a form of bracketing, or, "phenomenological reduction." Thus, as the oneness expression is then capable of being factored out within the square roots and interchangeable with the v -curvature expression herein. The complex field is not explicitly required for the phenomenological velocity solution method I demonstrate, but complex solutions are implied for variables in the system of equations. For background, Phenomenological Velocity exists as an optional interpretable real space, "hidden dimension," that forms a complete field with instantaneous (derivative) velocity via a trigonometric identity (Conditional Integral of Phenomenological Velocity, Emmerson 2023). Even though you can cancel out the Lorentz coefficient, and that is entirely agreed upon by the algebraic community, we can still solve for v implicitly by a modus ponens expression for one, and this is what is demonstrated in this paper. The paper is important, because it points out a missing solution that Mathematica has overlooked. Ignoring this solution could send an FTL spaceship vastly off course or into danger of the event horizon.

Formulation of Initial Setup:

$$h = \frac{\sqrt{-q^2 + 2qs - s^2 + l^2 \alpha^2}}{\alpha} = l \sin[\beta]$$

$$h = l \sin[\beta] == \frac{\sqrt{(l\alpha + x\gamma - r\theta)} \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \sqrt{(l\alpha - x\gamma + r\theta)} / \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}{\alpha}$$

$$c := 2.99792458 \cdot 10^8$$

The Solution Provided by Mathematica

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{In[]:= } & \text{Solve}\left[l \sin[\beta] == \frac{\sqrt{(l \alpha + x \gamma - r \theta)} \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \sqrt{(l \alpha - x \gamma + r \theta)} / \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}{\alpha}, v\right] \\
 & \left\{ \left\{ v \rightarrow - \left(\left(1. \sqrt{(-8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} x^2 \gamma^2 - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} r x \gamma \theta + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} r^2 \theta^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 \sin[\beta]^2)} \right) \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. \left(\sqrt{(-1. l^2 \alpha^2 + x^2 \gamma^2 - 2. r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2 + l^2 \alpha^2 \sin[\beta]^2)} \right) \right) \right\}, \\
 & \left\{ v \rightarrow v \rightarrow \left(\sqrt{(-8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} x^2 \gamma^2 - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} r x \gamma \theta + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} r^2 \theta^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 \sin[\beta]^2)} \right) \right. \\
 & \left. \left(\sqrt{-1. l^2 \alpha^2 + x^2 \gamma^2 - 2. r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2 + l^2 \alpha^2 \sin[\beta]^2} \right) \right\}
 \end{aligned}$$

Complex Solution to Distance, l

$$\text{In[]:= } \text{Solve}\left[l \sin[\beta] == \frac{\sqrt{(l \alpha + x \gamma - r \theta)} \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \sqrt{(l \alpha - x \gamma + r \theta)} / \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}{\alpha}, l\right]$$

$$\text{Out[]:= } \left\{ \left\{ l \rightarrow - \frac{i (x \gamma - r \theta)}{\alpha \sqrt{-1 + \sin[\beta]^2}} \right\}, \left\{ l \rightarrow \frac{i (x \gamma - r \theta)}{\alpha \sqrt{-1 + \sin[\beta]^2}} \right\} \right\}$$

$$\text{In[]:= } \text{Solve}\left[l \sin[\beta] == \frac{\sqrt{(l \alpha + x \gamma - r \theta)} \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \sqrt{(l \alpha - x \gamma + r \theta)} / \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}{\alpha}, l\right]$$

$$\text{In[]:= } c := 2.99792458 \cdot 10^8$$

$$\text{In[]:= } \text{Solve}\left[l \sin[\beta] == \frac{\sqrt{(l \alpha + x \gamma - r \theta)} \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \sqrt{(l \alpha - x \gamma + r \theta)} / \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}{\alpha}, l\right]$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Out[]:= } & \left\{ \left\{ l \rightarrow - \left(\left((0. + 1. i) \sqrt{(-8.98755 \times 10^{16} x^2 \gamma^2 + 1. v^2 x^2 \gamma^2 + 1.79751 \times 10^{17} r x \gamma \theta - 2. r v^2 x \gamma \theta - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} r^2 \theta^2 + 1. r^2 v^2 \theta^2)} \right) \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left(\alpha \sqrt{8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2} \right) \right) \right\}, \\
 & \left\{ l \rightarrow \left((0. + 1. i) \sqrt{(-8.98755 \times 10^{16} x^2 \gamma^2 + 1. v^2 x^2 \gamma^2 + 1.79751 \times 10^{17} r x \gamma \theta - 2. r v^2 x \gamma \theta - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} r^2 \theta^2 + 1. r^2 v^2 \theta^2)} \right) \right. \\
 & \left. \left(\alpha \sqrt{8.98755 \times 10^{16} - 1. v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin[\beta]^2 + v^2 \sin[\beta]^2} \right) \right\}
 \end{aligned}$$

In[]:= c := 2.99792458 * 10^8

Moving from the Initial Set-up to the Form of the Numerator

$$\text{In[]:= Solve}\left[l \text{Sin}[\beta] == \frac{\sqrt{(l \alpha + x \gamma - r \theta)} \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \sqrt{(l \alpha - x \gamma + r \theta)} / \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}{\alpha}, v\right]$$

$$\text{Out[]:= } \left\{ \left\{ v \rightarrow \left(\left(1. \sqrt{(-8.98755 \times 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} x^2 \gamma^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} r x \gamma \theta + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} r^2 \theta^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)} \right) / \left(\sqrt{-1. l^2 \alpha^2 + x^2 \gamma^2 - 2. r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2 + l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2} \right) \right\}, \left\{ v \rightarrow \left(\sqrt{(-8.98755 \times 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} x^2 \gamma^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} r x \gamma \theta + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} r^2 \theta^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)} \right) / \left(\sqrt{-1. l^2 \alpha^2 + x^2 \gamma^2 - 2. r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2 + l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2} \right) \right\} \right\}$$

$$l \text{Sin}[\beta] == \frac{\sqrt{l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2}}{\alpha}$$

$$l^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 == \frac{l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2}{\alpha^2}$$

$$l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 == l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2$$

$$l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 == l^2 \alpha^2 - (x \gamma - r \theta)^2$$

$$0 == l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2 - l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2$$

$$-l^2 \alpha^2 == -x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2 - l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2$$

$$-l^2 \alpha^2 + x^2 \gamma^2 == 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2 - l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2$$

$$-l^2 \alpha^2 + x^2 \gamma^2 - 2 r x \gamma \theta == -r^2 \theta^2 - l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2$$

$$-l^2 \alpha^2 + x^2 \gamma^2 - 2 r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2 == -l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2$$

$$-l^2 \alpha^2 + x^2 \gamma^2 - 2 r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2 + l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 == 0$$

$$c (-l^2 \alpha^2 + x^2 \gamma^2 - 2 r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2 + l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2) == 0$$

$$\text{In[]:= Distribute}\left[c^{\wedge}2 (-l^2 \alpha^2 + x^2 \gamma^2 - 2 r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2 + l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)\right]$$

$$\text{Out[]:= } -8.98755 \times 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} x^2 \gamma^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} r x \gamma \theta + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} r^2 \theta^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2$$

Demonstrating Equivalence of Numerator and Denominator

$$\sqrt{\left(-8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} x^2 \gamma^2 - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} r x \gamma \theta + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} r^2 \theta^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 \sin[\beta]^2\right)} = 0$$

$$\left(\sqrt{\left(-8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} x^2 \gamma^2 - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} r x \gamma \theta + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} r^2 \theta^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 \sin[\beta]^2\right)}\right) == \left(l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2 - l^2 \alpha^2 \sin[\beta]^2\right)$$

$$\left(\sqrt{\left(-8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} x^2 \gamma^2 - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} r x \gamma \theta + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} r^2 \theta^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 \sin[\beta]^2\right)}\right) / \left(l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2 - l^2 \alpha^2 \sin[\beta]^2\right) = 1$$

$$\text{In[]:= } \left(\sqrt{\left(-8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} x^2 \gamma^2 - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} r x \gamma \theta + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} r^2 \theta^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 \sin[\beta]^2\right)}\right) / \left(l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2 - l^2 \alpha^2 \sin[\beta]^2\right)$$

$$\text{Out[]:= } \left(\sqrt{\left(-8.98755 \times 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} x^2 \gamma^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} r x \gamma \theta + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} r^2 \theta^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 \sin[\beta]^2\right)}\right) / \left(l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2 - l^2 \alpha^2 \sin[\beta]^2\right)$$

$$\text{In[]:= } \left(\sqrt{\left(-8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} x^2 \gamma^2 - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} r x \gamma \theta + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} r^2 \theta^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 \sin[\beta]^2\right)}\right) / \left(\sqrt{-1. \cdot l^2 \alpha^2 + x^2 \gamma^2 - 2. \cdot r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2 + l^2 \alpha^2 \sin[\beta]^2}\right)$$

$$\text{Out[]:= } \left(\sqrt{\left(-8.98755 \times 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} x^2 \gamma^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} r x \gamma \theta + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} r^2 \theta^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 \sin[\beta]^2\right)}\right) / \left(\sqrt{-1. \cdot l^2 \alpha^2 + x^2 \gamma^2 - 2. \cdot r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2 + l^2 \alpha^2 \sin[\beta]^2}\right)$$

Justification for Solution:

Now, we write :

$$\text{Solve}[\text{l Sin}[\beta] == \frac{\sqrt{(l\alpha + x\gamma - r\theta)} \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \sqrt{(l\alpha - x\gamma + r\theta)} / \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}{\alpha}, v]$$

$$\text{Solve}[\text{l Sin}[\beta] == \frac{\sqrt{(l\alpha + x\gamma - r\theta)} \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} (l\alpha - x\gamma + r\theta) / \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}{\alpha}, v]$$

$$\text{Solve}[\text{l Sin}[\beta] == \frac{\sqrt{(l\alpha + x\gamma - r\theta)} (l\alpha - x\gamma + r\theta) (1)}{\alpha}, v]$$

$$\text{Solve}[\text{l Sin}[\beta] == \frac{\sqrt{(l\alpha + x\gamma - r\theta)} (l\alpha - x\gamma + r\theta) (1)}{\alpha}, v]$$

$$\begin{aligned} & (\sqrt{(-8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 + \\ & \quad 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} x^2 \gamma^2 - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} r x \gamma \theta + \\ & \quad 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} r^2 \theta^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)}) / \\ & (l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2 - l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2) = 1 \end{aligned}$$

So, because both can equal 1, the solution to v can be logically interpreted.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Solve}[\text{l Sin}[\beta] == & \frac{1}{\alpha} \sqrt{((l\alpha + x\gamma - r\theta) (l\alpha - x\gamma + r\theta) \\ & ((\sqrt{(-8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} x^2 \gamma^2 - \\ & \quad 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} r x \gamma \theta + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} r^2 \theta^2 + \\ & \quad 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2)})) / \\ & (l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2 - l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2))}, v] \end{aligned}$$

Application of Solution to Initial Conditions (Full Cancellation):

$$\text{Solve}\left[l \text{Sin}[\beta] == \frac{1}{\alpha} \sqrt{\left((l \alpha + x \gamma - r \theta) \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. \sqrt{\left(1 - \frac{1}{c^2} \left(\left(\sqrt{(-8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} x^2 \gamma^2 - \right. \right. \right. \right. \right. \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. \left. \left. \left. 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} r x \gamma \theta + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} r^2 \theta^2 + \right. \right. \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. \left. 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 \right) \right) \right) / \right. \\ \left. \left. \left(l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2 - l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 \right) \right)^2 \right) (l \alpha - x \gamma + r \theta) / \right. \\ \left. \sqrt{\left(1 - \frac{1}{c^2} \left(\left(\sqrt{(-8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} x^2 \gamma^2 - \right. \right. \right. \right. \right. \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. \left. \left. \left. 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} r x \gamma \theta + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} r^2 \theta^2 + \right. \right. \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. \left. 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 \right) \right) \right) / \right. \\ \left. \left. \left(l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2 - l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 \right) \right)^2 \right) \right], v]$$

$$l \text{Sin}[\beta] == \frac{1}{\alpha} \sqrt{\left((l \alpha + x \gamma - r \theta) \right. \\ \left. \sqrt{\left(1 - \frac{1}{c^2} \left(\left(\sqrt{(-8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} x^2 \gamma^2 - \right. \right. \right. \right. \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. \left. \left. \left. 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} r x \gamma \theta + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} r^2 \theta^2 + \right. \right. \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. \left. 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 \right) \right) \right) / \right. \\ \left. \left. \left(l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2 - l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 \right) \right)^2 \right) (l \alpha - x \gamma + r \theta) / \right. \\ \left. \sqrt{\left(1 - \frac{1}{c^2} \left(\left(\sqrt{(-8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} x^2 \gamma^2 - \right. \right. \right. \right. \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. \left. \left. \left. 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} r x \gamma \theta + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} r^2 \theta^2 + \right. \right. \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. \left. 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 \right) \right) \right) / \right. \\ \left. \left. \left(l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2 - l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 \right) \right)^2 \right) \right) ==$$

$$\frac{\sqrt{\sqrt{1 - 1.1126500560536185 \cdot 10^{-17} v^2} (l \alpha + x \gamma - r \theta)} \sqrt{\frac{l \alpha - x \gamma + r \theta}{\sqrt{1 - 1.1126500560536185 \cdot 10^{-17} v^2}}}}{\alpha},$$

$$\text{In}[*]:= \frac{1}{\alpha}$$

$$\sqrt{\left((l\alpha + x\gamma - r\theta) \sqrt{\left(1 - \frac{1}{c^2} \left(\sqrt{(-8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} x^2 \gamma^2 - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} r x \gamma \theta + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} r^2 \theta^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 \sin[\beta]^2)} \right)} \right) / \left(l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2 - l^2 \alpha^2 \sin[\beta]^2 \right)^2 \right) (l\alpha - x\gamma + r\theta) / \sqrt{\left(1 - \frac{1}{c^2} \left(\sqrt{(-8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} x^2 \gamma^2 - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} r x \gamma \theta + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} r^2 \theta^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 \sin[\beta]^2)} \right)} \right) / \left(l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2 - l^2 \alpha^2 \sin[\beta]^2 \right)^2 \right) \right)}$$

$$\text{Out}[*]= \frac{\sqrt{(l\alpha + x\gamma - r\theta) (l\alpha - x\gamma + r\theta)}}{\alpha}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{In[]:= } & \frac{1}{\alpha} \sqrt{\left(\sqrt{\left(1 - 1.1126500560536185 \cdot 10^{-17} \right.} \right. \\
 & \left. \left(\left(\sqrt{\left(-8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} x^2 \gamma^2 - \right.} \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. \left. 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} r x \gamma \theta + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} r^2 \theta^2 + \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. \left. 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 \right) \right) \right) / \\
 & \left. \left(\sqrt{-1. \cdot l^2 \alpha^2 + x^2 \gamma^2 - 2. \cdot r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2 + l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2} \right) \right)^2 \left(l \alpha + x \gamma - r \theta \right) \Big) \\
 & \sqrt{\left((l \alpha - x \gamma + r \theta) / \left(\sqrt{\left(1 - 1.1126500560536185 \cdot 10^{-17} \right.} \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left(\left(\sqrt{\left(-8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} x^2 \gamma^2 - \right.} \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. \left. 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} r x \gamma \theta + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} r^2 \theta^2 + \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. \left. 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 \right) \right) \right) / \\
 & \left. \left(\sqrt{-1. \cdot l^2 \alpha^2 + x^2 \gamma^2 - 2. \cdot r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2 + l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2} \right) \right)^2 \Big) \Big) \Big)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Out[]:= } & \frac{1}{\alpha} \sqrt{\left((l \alpha - x \gamma + r \theta) / \right. \\
 & \left(\sqrt{\left(1 - (1.11265 \times 10^{-17} (-8.98755 \times 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} x^2 \gamma^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17} \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. \left. r x \gamma \theta + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} r^2 \theta^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 \right) \right) / \right. \\
 & \left. \left. (-1. l^2 \alpha^2 + x^2 \gamma^2 - 2. r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2 + l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2) \right) \right) \Big) \\
 & \sqrt{\left((l \alpha + x \gamma - r \theta) \sqrt{\left(1 - (1.11265 \times 10^{-17} (-8.98755 \times 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} x^2 \gamma^2 - \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. \left. 1.79751 \times 10^{17} r x \gamma \theta + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} r^2 \theta^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2) \right) \right) / \right. \\
 & \left. \left. (-1. l^2 \alpha^2 + x^2 \gamma^2 - 2. r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2 + l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2) \right) \right) \Big)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left\{ \left\{ v \rightarrow - \left(\left(1. \cdot \sqrt{\left(-8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 + \right.} \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. \left. 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} x^2 \gamma^2 - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} r x \gamma \theta + \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. \left. 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} r^2 \theta^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 \right) \right) \right) / \right. \\
 & \left. \left(\sqrt{\left(-1. \cdot l^2 \alpha^2 + x^2 \gamma^2 - 2. \cdot r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2 + l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 \right) \right) \right) \Big\}, \\
 & \left\{ v \rightarrow v \rightarrow \left(\sqrt{\left(-8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} x^2 \gamma^2 - \right.} \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. \left. 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} r x \gamma \theta + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} r^2 \theta^2 + \right. \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. \left. 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2 \right) \right) \right) / \\
 & \left. \left(\sqrt{-1. \cdot l^2 \alpha^2 + x^2 \gamma^2 - 2. \cdot r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2 + l^2 \alpha^2 \text{Sin}[\beta]^2} \right) \right) \Big\}
 \end{aligned}$$

Now there is a third solution to v, which Mathematica has ignored . That solution is that v is undefined, and provably

SO .

The deduction :

$$l^2 \alpha^2 \sin[\beta]^2 = l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2$$

$$l^2 \alpha^2 \sin[\beta]^2 = l^2 \alpha^2 - (x \gamma - r \theta)^2$$

$$0 = l^2 \alpha^2 - x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2 - l^2 \alpha^2 \sin[\beta]^2$$

$$-l^2 \alpha^2 = -x^2 \gamma^2 + 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2 - l^2 \alpha^2 \sin[\beta]^2$$

$$-l^2 \alpha^2 + x^2 \gamma^2 = 2 r x \gamma \theta - r^2 \theta^2 - l^2 \alpha^2 \sin[\beta]^2$$

$$-l^2 \alpha^2 + x^2 \gamma^2 - 2 r x \gamma \theta = -r^2 \theta^2 - l^2 \alpha^2 \sin[\beta]^2$$

$$-l^2 \alpha^2 + x^2 \gamma^2 - 2 r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2 = -l^2 \alpha^2 \sin[\beta]^2$$

$$-l^2 \alpha^2 + x^2 \gamma^2 - 2 r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2 + l^2 \alpha^2 \sin[\beta]^2 = 0$$

$$c (-l^2 \alpha^2 + x^2 \gamma^2 - 2 r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2 + l^2 \alpha^2 \sin[\beta]^2) = 0$$

Demonstrates that although we can logically equate the forms,
and bypass the inference that v is undefined,

we need to acknowledge that there is a third solution,

$$\frac{0}{0} = \frac{c (-l^2 \alpha^2 + x^2 \gamma^2 - 2 r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2 + l^2 \alpha^2 \sin[\beta]^2)}{-l^2 \alpha^2 + x^2 \gamma^2 - 2 r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2 + l^2 \alpha^2 \sin[\beta]^2} =$$

$$\text{In[50]:= } \frac{c (-l^2 \alpha^2 + x^2 \gamma^2 - 2 r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2 + l^2 \alpha^2 \sin[\beta]^2)}{-l^2 \alpha^2 + x^2 \gamma^2 - 2 r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2 + l^2 \alpha^2 \sin[\beta]^2}$$

$$\text{Out[50]= } 2.99792 \times 10^8$$

$$\text{In[51]:= } \text{Distribute}[c (-l^2 \alpha^2 + x^2 \gamma^2 - 2 r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2 + l^2 \alpha^2 \sin[\beta]^2)]$$

$$\text{Out[51]= } -2.99792 \times 10^8 l^2 \alpha^2 + 2.99792 \times 10^8 x^2 \gamma^2 - \\ 5.99585 \times 10^8 r x \gamma \theta + 2.99792 \times 10^8 r^2 \theta^2 + 2.99792 \times 10^8 l^2 \alpha^2 \sin[\beta]^2$$

$$\text{In[52]:= } \text{Distribute}[c^2 (-l^2 \alpha^2 + x^2 \gamma^2 - 2 r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2 + l^2 \alpha^2 \sin[\beta]^2)]$$

$$\text{Out[52]= } -8.98755 \times 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} x^2 \gamma^2 - \\ 1.79751 \times 10^{17} r x \gamma \theta + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} r^2 \theta^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 \sin[\beta]^2$$

$$\frac{0}{0} = \frac{c (-l^2 \alpha^2 + x^2 \gamma^2 - 2 r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2 + l^2 \alpha^2 \sin[\beta]^2)}{-l^2 \alpha^2 + x^2 \gamma^2 - 2 r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2 + l^2 \alpha^2 \sin[\beta]^2} = -8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2 +$$

$$8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} x^2 \gamma^2 - 1.7975103574736352 \cdot 10^{17} r x \gamma \theta +$$

$$8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} r^2 \theta^2 + 8.987551787368176 \cdot 10^{16} l^2 \alpha^2$$

$$\sin[\beta]^2 / (-l^2 \alpha^2 + x^2 \gamma^2 - 2 r x \gamma \theta + r^2 \theta^2 + l^2 \alpha^2 \sin[\beta]^2) = \text{Undefined}$$

Conclusion

Strictly speaking, the solution to Phenomenal Velocity, v (and yes, it can be interpreted as velocity (Conditional Integral of Phenomenological Velocity (Emmerson, 2023))), does not require use of the complex field, but rather Modus Ponens suffices. There are complex solutions to the algebraic architecture established by the permissible injection of the Lorentz Coefficient, but these are only, “tangentially,” correspondent to the original form of the equation.

We can think of the oneness as that oneness of a singularity, while the Undefined solution, we can think of it as the Undefined aspect of the event horizon.

Going from V to Imaginary Length

Parker Emmerson

September 2024

1 Introduction

$$v\sqrt{-1.0l^2\alpha^2 + x^2\gamma^2 - 2.0rx\gamma\theta + r^2\theta^2 + l^2\alpha^2 \sin^2(\beta)} =$$

$$\sqrt{-8.98755 \times 10^{16}l^2\alpha^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16}x^2\gamma^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17}rx\gamma\theta + 8.98755 \times 10^{16}r^2\theta^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16}l^2\alpha^2 \sin^2(\beta)}$$

Step 1: Square Both Sides Square both sides to eliminate the square roots:

$$(v\sqrt{-1.0l^2\alpha^2 + x^2\gamma^2 - 2.0rx\gamma\theta + r^2\theta^2 + l^2\alpha^2 \sin^2(\beta)})^2 =$$

$$\left(\sqrt{-8.98755 \times 10^{16}l^2\alpha^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16}x^2\gamma^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17}rx\gamma\theta + 8.98755 \times 10^{16}r^2\theta^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16}l^2\alpha^2 \sin^2(\beta)}\right)^2$$

This simplifies to:

$$v^2(-1.0l^2\alpha^2 + x^2\gamma^2 - 2.0rx\gamma\theta + r^2\theta^2 + l^2\alpha^2 \sin^2(\beta)) =$$

$$-8.98755 \times 10^{16}l^2\alpha^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16}x^2\gamma^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17}rx\gamma\theta + 8.98755 \times 10^{16}r^2\theta^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16}l^2\alpha^2 \sin^2(\beta)$$

Step 2: Distribute v^2 on the Left Side Expand the left-hand side by distributing v^2 :

$$-1.0v^2l^2\alpha^2 + v^2x^2\gamma^2 - 2.0v^2rx\gamma\theta + v^2r^2\theta^2 + v^2l^2\alpha^2 \sin^2(\beta)$$

Step 3: Matching Terms Now we need to equate the terms on both sides:

$$-1.0v^2l^2\alpha^2 + v^2x^2\gamma^2 - 2.0v^2rx\gamma\theta + v^2r^2\theta^2 + v^2l^2\alpha^2 \sin^2(\beta) =$$

$$-8.98755 \times 10^{16}l^2\alpha^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16}x^2\gamma^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17}rx\gamma\theta + 8.98755 \times 10^{16}r^2\theta^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16}l^2\alpha^2 \sin^2(\beta)$$

Step 4: Equate Coefficients Collecting terms involving l^2 , $x^2\gamma^2$, $rx\gamma\theta$, and $r^2\theta^2$, isolate l^2 :

$$-1.0v^2l^2\alpha^2 + v^2l^2\alpha^2 \sin^2(\beta) = -8.98755 \times 10^{16}l^2\alpha^2 + 8.98755 \times 10^{16}l^2\alpha^2 \sin^2(\beta)$$

Step 5: Find a Common Denominator and Further Simplify Group $l^2\alpha^2$ terms and simplify:

$$-1.0v^2 + v^2 \sin^2(\beta) = -8.98755 \times 10^{16} + 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin^2(\beta)$$

Simplifying the equation for l^2 :

$$l^2(-v^2\alpha^2 + v^2\alpha^2 \sin^2(\beta) + 8.98755 \times 10^{16}\alpha^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16}\alpha^2 \sin^2(\beta)) =$$

$$(8.98755 \times 10^{16}x^2\gamma^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17}rx\gamma\theta + 8.98755 \times 10^{16}r^2\theta^2 - v^2x^2\gamma^2 + 2v^2rx\gamma\theta - v^2r^2\theta^2)$$

Step 6: Solve for l Divide both sides by the factor:

$$l^2 = \frac{8.98755 \times 10^{16}x^2\gamma^2 - 1.79751 \times 10^{17}rx\gamma\theta + 8.98755 \times 10^{16}r^2\theta^2 - v^2x^2\gamma^2 + 2.0v^2rx\gamma\theta - v^2r^2\theta^2}{8.98755 \times 10^{16}(1 - \sin^2(\beta)) - v^2(1 - \sin^2(\beta))}$$

Since $\sin^2(\beta) = 1 - \cos^2(\beta)$, simplify to:

$$l = \pm \frac{\sqrt{-8.98755 \times 10^{16} x^2 \gamma^2 + v^2 x^2 \gamma^2 + 1.79751 \times 10^{17} r x \gamma \theta - 2.0 r v^2 x \gamma \theta - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} r^2 \theta^2 + v^2 r^2 \theta^2}}{\sqrt{(8.98755 \times 10^{16} - v^2) - (8.98755 \times 10^{16} - v^2) \sin^2(\beta)}}$$

Step 7: Final Form The corresponding solutions are:

$$l = \pm \frac{(0.+1.I)\sqrt{-8.98755 \times 10^{16} x^2 \gamma^2 + v^2 x^2 \gamma^2 + 1.79751 \times 10^{17} r x \gamma \theta - 2. r v^2 x \gamma \theta - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} r^2 \theta^2 + v^2 r^2 \theta^2}}{\alpha \sqrt{8.98755 \times 10^{16} - v^2 - 8.98755 \times 10^{16} \sin^2(\beta) + v^2 \sin^2(\beta)}}$$